

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE HIGH-CONDUCTIVITY ELECTRICAL ANOMALY IN THE CARPATHIAN REGION

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Introduction

The Carpathian high electrical conductivity anomaly was identified by Wiese H. (1962) and studied extensively in international projects by many researchers who wanted to unravel its main features. The Carpathian high conductivity electrical anomaly is considered to be influenced by many factors, such as a compressional regime influenced by the tectonic activity in the transition zone between the Carpathian Orogen, the Moesian Platform, the Eastern European Platform and the Scythian Platform. The Carpathian high electrical conductivity anomaly (CECA), also called geoelectric anomaly, is attributed to the contact area situated at a variable depth, with strongly tectonized and faulted crystalline basement (high resistivity).

Geological and tectonic settings

The Carpathian Mountains are part of the Alpino-Himalayan orogen that formed about 35 million years ago due to alpine Tertiary orogenic processes resulting from the convergence and collision of several microplates with the Eurasian plate during the closing of the Tethys Ocean (Săndulescu, 1984; Hauser et al., 2007). The Romanian Carpathians represent a compressive belt formed in the late Cenozoic. The movement of rock bodies, independent of their masses and the tectonic causes that cause the Carpathian Orogen displacement, is related to the evolution of the Eastern Alps and the Pannonian basin (Linzer et al., 1996), hypothesis which is based on the retrograde subduction of an oceanic lithosphere.

Methods and models

The geophysical-geological models of the Carpathian system represent a young orogenic area surrounded by older stable platforms. The conductivity anomalies detected from the crust and the upper mantle have different dimensions. Their spatial position is related to many factors directly influenced by the geological-tectonic and physico-chemical past of the site.

The electrical conductivities are determined to establish the material composition of the geological environment, the physical and geodynamic state of the area. All studies of these anomalies require a description of the parameters of the conductive zones. In the case of conductivity anomalies only their presence can be specified (Ádám, 1980).

The most credible hypothesis for the Carpathian high conductivity electrical anomaly was given by Rokityansky et al. (1986). According to this hypothesis, the anomaly may be related to the metamorphic processes to which the sedimentary rocks were subjected, at high temperatures and pressures at depths of over 10-25 km. The sediments were submerged along the subduction zones and during heating, the process was accompanied by dehydration and partial melting.

Laboratory experiments have shown that the strongest melting (amphibolite phase) following metamorphic processes occurs at temperatures 400-700°C. Magnetotelluric measurements indicated in active tectonic areas the presence of a high electrical conductivity layer at depths of about 20-40 km (Rokityansky, 1986).

Carpathian high electrical conductivity anomaly, also referred to as geoelectric anomaly, is attributed to the presence of rocks with high conductivity, located at a depth varying from 10 to 25 km. The tectonized and faulted portion of the Precambrian basement (high resistivity) in the Polish Carpathian area (20 km deep) was identified based on the results of the magnetotelluric surveys (MTS). The source of the Carpathian geoelectric anomaly is considered to be located near the collision suture. In the Ukrainian Carpathians area a different interpretation was considered for CECA: deep saline solutions (Rokityansky, 2014).

Fig. 1 Map of electrical conductivity anomalies in Central Europe (compiled after Porstendorfer et al., 1976; Rokityansky et al., 1976b; Pinna et al., 1992; coal basins after the Tectonique Internationale de l'Europe, 1982; Pożaryski & Dembowski, 1984; and Oszczytko et al., 1989).

1 - extension of the upper carboniferous, coal-layers, 2 - the crystalline-mesozoic zone of the Eastern Carpathians (the northern part - the Maramures massif), 3 - conductivity anomalies (**NGP** - North-German-Polish, **C**-Carpathian (red line), **RG**-Upper Rhine Graben - Gottingen), 4 - Carpathian frontal push, 5 - **PKB**-Pieniny Klippen Belt (Zytko, 1997)

The continental crust contains structures of different sizes developed both lateral and vertical, some of them are anisotropic. The areas where the conductivity anomalies identified within large materially interconnected structures, interstitially within a host matrix from the deep crust, regardless of the source of the geological material, are attributed to intergranular graphite coated films; this observation began to emerge in Adam's studies (1978), Shankland and Ander (1983), (Schwarz G, 1990).

The main factor that generates the Carpathian geoelectric anomaly is the graphite produced after the post-oligocene migration. The anomaly is linked to the presence of the carriers of an association of hydrothermal minerals. Such filons are present everywhere in the Carpathians, near the axis of the anomaly, (Zytko, 1997).

The true depth of the upper edge of the anomalies was defined by the MTS method only in three locations (Slovakia, Ukraine, and Romania), 25-40 years ago. The purpose of future CECA research should be to study its nature (fluids or minerals) (Rokityansky, 2014).

The geophysical information obtained by the MTS method in the Carpathian orogen and surrounding areas provides an lithospheric model along a profile that runs, from west to east, the Transylvanian Depression, the Neogene Volcanic Chain, the Nappe of the Flysch, the Foreland Platform and the Moesian and Scythian Platforms. The model developed reveals the paleo-alpine plan of "consumption" caused by the collision of two lithospheric plates that generated the subduction of the Eastern Carpathians. The magnetotelluric studies in Romania started at the end of the 1970s, only 8 profiles crossed the CECA. Over the Carpathians were traced 20 profiles. The geophysical methods used were various (MT, MTS, and MTP), (Stănică et al., 1993, Stănică et al. 1999). The increase in electrical conductivity in the compressive area can be attributed to the presence of the Graphite system shale fixed along the paleo-alpine plane of "consumption" as a result of the compressive regime and tectonic activity. The grafitic areas are considered tectonic markers, possibly related to the old hypothesis collision areas supported by Korja T. and Stănică D.

Fig. 2 Hilbert transformation of induction arrows over Europe at the period of $T = 1800$ s based on data from ca. 1800 sites (Wybraniec et al. 1999). Conductivity anomalies: **SS** = Storavan-Skellefteå, **BS** = Bothnia-Satakunta, **LLBB** = Lake Ladoga—Bothnian Bay, **KA** = Kirovograd Anomaly, **CCA** = Carpathian Conductivity Anomaly, **NGP** = North German—Polish anomaly (Korja, 2007)

We can distinguish two anomalies of high electrical conductivity (Fig. 2) characterized by similar physical properties: one in the Eastern Carpathians influenced by the compressional tectonic processes (continent-continent collision). The second high electrical conductivity anomaly corresponds to the peri-Carpathian fault in the Southern and Eastern Carpathians. In the Carpathian bend area it descends with crystalline basement; it is shielded by the sedimentary cover which is very thick (over 20 km) and deviated to the east.

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